

Challenges Facing Implementation of Science Program in FCT Secondary Schools, Abuja, Nigeria

Ogunode Niyi Jacob¹

Academic Planning Officer, Federal University Wukari, Nigeria

Email: Ogunodejacob@gmail.com

Deborah Jegede

Post-graduate Student, University of Abuja, Nigeria

Email: Jegededeborah30@gmail.com

Abstract: The study investigated the challenges facing the implementation of science programs in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria. The questionnaire was adopted for the study by the researchers. We used a descriptive survey design for the study. Simple sampling methods were used to select 140 respondents from the entire population of science teachers in FCT, Abuja. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the use of test and re-test method. Mean, simple percentage and chi-square were used to analyze and test the hypotheses. Data/information were collected and analyzed. The result collected from the study led to the conclusion that majority of the sampled respondents agreed that inadequate science teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, inadequate instructional materials, poor planning and ineffective supervision are the challenges to the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. Based on these findings, the researchers recommend that the government should increase the funding of science education in FCT.

Keyword: Challenges, Implementation, Science program, etc.

Introduction:

Nigeria, gigantic Africa with over 200 million population got her independence in 1960. Nigeria is blessed with over 250 ethnic groups with three major languages which are the Houses, the Igbo's and the Yoruba's. Nigeria has 36 states with Federal capital territory and 774 local government councils.

The educational system of Nigeria comprises of the early education, basic education, junior secondary schools education and the senior secondary school education and higher education. Adolphus, (2019) observes that Nigeria runs the 6-3-3-4 system of education with 6 years of primary education (ages 6-12), 3 years of junior secondary (ages 13-15), 3 years of senior secondary (ages 16-18) and 4 years of university education. However, engineering and medical-related courses in the university take 5 or 6 years respectively. In Nigeria, the first 6 years of schooling at the primary level and the first 3 years of secondary make up the 9 years of basic, free and compulsory education referred to as the Universal Basic Education (FRN, 2013). It is important to note that in Nigeria, admission into schools is not strictly by age, so it is not unlikely to have a range of 5 years of age difference in any class cohort.

¹ Corresponding author

According to the National policy on education (2004) Secondary Education is defined as the education that children receive after primary education and before the tertiary education. Based on the 6-3-3-4 system of education, secondary education comprises six years duration, but given in two stages: a junior secondary school stage and a senior secondary school stage, each to run for three years duration.

The broad goals of Secondary Education according to the National Policy on Education (2004) include the preparation of the individual for:

- i. Useful living within the society, and
- ii. Higher education.

In specific terms, the objectives are to:

- i. provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religion or ethnic background;
- ii. Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles;
- iii. Provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades;
- iv. Develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world cultural heritage;
- v. Inspire its students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence;
- vi. Foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity;

According to Legit, (2018) new Nigerian curriculum for secondary schools includes English studies (compulsory subject); Mathematics (compulsory subject); Civic Education (compulsory subject); Trade/Entrepreneurship Studies (compulsory subject, the student can choose one of 34 subjects); Humanities (Every student can choose 2, 3, 4 or 5 subjects depending on his or her potential); Science & Mathematics (Every student can choose 2, 3, 4 or 5 subjects); Technology (Every student can choose 2, 3, 4 or 5 subjects); Business Studies (Senior) (Every student can choose 2, 3, 4 or 5 subjects). The main idea of a new curriculum is to provide more practical experience for students.

The science programs include Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Further Mathematics, Technology, Technical Drawing etc. Science programs in Nigerian schools are given maximum attention due to their significant contribution to the technological development of the country. (Adolphus, 2019) opines that in Nigeria, science is taught and learnt as Basic Science and Technology from primary to junior secondary levels, and as biology, chemistry and physics for three years in the senior secondary (SS) classes (SS1-3). The government recognizes the importance of science to the development of its young citizenry as demonstrated in the national policy and other curricula texts, "in recognition of the fundamental importance and cost-intensive nature of science, technology and trade/entrepreneurship, Government shall provide adequate funds for science, technology and trade/entrepreneurship education" (FME 2013).

Opara & David, (2014) observe that in all nations of the world (Nigeria inclusive), Science and Mathematics are given first-class attention due to numerous benefits derived from them. For

instance, the knowledge of drugs, diseases (their transmission, control and cure), reproduction, childbirth, environmental pollution, food production, number and numeracy, telecommunication, chemicals among many others are acquired through the study of Science and Mathematics (that is, technology) has led to the manufacture of many products and services computers, electronic gadgets airplanes, ships, weapons, automobiles, printing press, electrical appliances, mobile phones to mention a few, are all derived from the practical application of Science and Technology.

The objectives of science education in Nigeria have not been actually achieved due to many challenges facing the implementation of the program in the Nigerian educational institutions, especially in senior secondary schools.

One of the major challenges facing the Nigerian educational system is the problem of implementation. Many educational programs started in the country in past were poorly implemented. Due to poor implementation, sciences teachers cannot deliver effective teaching and science students cannot learn well because instructional aids and infrastructural facilities are not adequately supplied to implement the science programs as planned.

This study is aimed to investigate the challenges facing the implementation of science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem:

There are many policies formulated and planned to ensure that the science program in the Nigerian secondary schools are developed and achieved its aims and objectives but implementation these policies and program is a problem due to many challenges. According to (UNICEF,2017) Nigeria is a policy-rich environment but poor in implementation. The capacity and commitment of the government to implement educational policies and processes have been limited due to inadequate resources and political will. Nigeria Poor funding environment, weak governance and financial management, and low capacity may adversely impact on program implementation. Based on this submission, this study is aimed to investigate the challenges facing the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria.

Research Objectives:

The objectives of this study are to investigate the challenges facing the implementation of science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria. Specific objectives are to:

- i. To find out if the inadequate science teachers is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- ii. To find out if the inadequate funding is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja.
- iii. To find out if the inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- iv. To find out if the inadequate instructional materials is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja.
- v. To find out if poor planning is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- vi. To find out if ineffective supervision is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja.

Research Hypothesis:

Based on the research objectives raised for the study, the researchers developed the following hypotheses to guide the research:

- i. Inadequate science teachers is not a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja.
- ii. Inadequate funding is a not challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT secondary schools, Abuja.
- iii. Inadequate infrastructural facilities is a not challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- iv. Inadequate instructional materials is a not challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- v. Poor planning is a not challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.
- vi. Ineffective supervision is a not challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Literature Review:

Concept Of Secondary School And Science Program:

National Policy on Education (2004) views secondary education as the education that children receive after primary education and before the tertiary education. Based on the 6-3-3-4 system of education, secondary education comprises six years duration, but given in two stages: a junior secondary school stage and a senior secondary school stage, each to run for three years duration. Secondary school education is the education that prepares the learner for higher education. Secondary school education can also be defined as the education that introduces career specialization for the learners. The objectives of Secondary Education according to the National Policy on Education (2004) include the preparation of the individual for:

- i. Useful living within the society and
- ii. Higher education.

In specific terms, the objectives are to:

- i. provide all primary school leavers with the opportunity for education of a higher level, irrespective of sex, social status, religion or ethnic background;
- ii. Offer diversified curriculum to cater for the differences in talents, opportunities and future roles;
- iii. Provide trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional grades;
- iv. Develop and promote Nigerian languages, art and culture in the context of world cultural heritage;
- v. Inspire its students with a desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence;

- vi. Foster national unity with an emphasis on the common ties that unite us in our diversity;

Adolphus, (2019) submits that the purposes of science education in Nigeria are generally drawn from the national goals and philosophy of education as contained in the National Policy on Education (NPE). For instance, the goals of education in Nigeria include the Development of the individual into a morally sound, patriotic, and effective citizen; ...and social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of society (FRN 2013, p. 2). According to the national policy text, the goals of science education shall be to:

- i. Cultivate inquiring, knowing and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy
- ii. Produce scientist for national development
- iii. Service studies in technology and the cause of technological development; and
- iv. Provide knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the forms, and the conduct of life (Adolphus, 2019) cited (FRN 2004, p. 29).

The importance of science education to the social, economic, and technological development of the country cannot be underestimated. Sambo et al., (2014) observe that the importance of science and technology to national development in the life of any country cannot be overemphasized. This is because knowledge and skills in science and technology are very vital in the development of any society. Sambo et al., (2014) cited Mulemwa (2002) points out that, the fast-changing applications of science and technology and the global reliance on its processes and products in all areas of human endeavor have made them invaluable that any society or country without them risks being alienated from the global village. This means that for an individual to be well-grounded in science, and competent enough to face the challenges of life in his society, he or she must have gone through a science program that is well planned, assessed and implemented.

The search, collaboration, reporting, and communication skills provided by science education can yield a whole generation of people who are more prepared for their careers, such people can make better contributions to society. Furthermore, learners who have an in-depth knowledge of science education are more willing to use new ideas and technologies that can enhance and strengthen the economy. Through explaining and emphasizing the reliance of living organisms on one another and also on the environment, science education promotes intellectual respect for Mother Nature, This action can inform choice with regards to how technology is used to enhance the current living conditions for both humans and other living things (Christine & Hayatu, 2014)

The achievement that came about due to science education has resulted in longer and healthier lives. People who understand and honor or celebrate past scientific achievements are more likely to herald future inventions and discoveries that will enhance mental and physical health; besides, a healthier general public means a highly productive society. Science education encourages learners to reason critically so as to make better decisions that are well – informed. This makes them even more enlightened voters. The caution and responsibility provided by science education also assist people to become more responsible parents. There are no shortcomings of science education. In fact, good knowledge of scientific principles and facts is vital for a comprehensive education (Christine & Hayatu, 2014).

One of the greatest challenges facing science programs in Nigeria is poor implementation. Implementation is the act of carrying out a planned policy, program or project. Implementation is the process of executing an organized program for the development of society. Implementation in education is the systematic way of carrying out a planned educational policy, program and projects with the objectives of developing the educational sector.

There are many studies on the teaching and learning of science programs in secondary schools across the world, especially in Nigeria. Some of the studies include that of Opara & David (2014) that investigated the factors that affect teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology in primary schools. The population of the study consisted of 100 male and female teachers in primary schools. A survey research design was adopted for the study, three research questions, and two null hypotheses were formulated base on the specific purpose of the study. The data for the study were collected by means of a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The data collected were analyzed using the mean score to answer research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using a t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that most of the instructional materials were not available for teaching basic science in primary schools. The non-available of material implies their non-utilization. Primary school administrators should encourage classroom teachers to produce and use instructional materials in teaching. Teachers should not wait for the Government to do everything; they should go the extra mile in the provision of instructional materials for their pupils.

Fiifi, & Beatrice (2013) observed that their research is an investigative and explorative study that looked into the challenges of teaching Integrated Science in the public Junior High Schools in the Kwahu West Municipality. The study took a look at the challenges that might exist to hinder the performances of the science teachers. All the 60 Integrated Science teachers, the 50 heads of public Junior High Schools as well as the eight circuit supervisors and science coordinators in the Municipality were purposively selected for the study. A descriptive survey design was used for the study. Data were collected with a set of questionnaires and an interview schedule and were analyzed using frequencies and percentages. The results indicated that the science teachers faced some challenges in dealing with the content of Integrated Science in Junior High Schools. It was, therefore, recommended that there is a need for regular organization of professional development activities such as induction and in-services by the Ghana Education Services to help them deal with the challenges.

Christine, & Hayatu (2014) did a study that investigated the problems and prospects in the learning of basic science in the upper basic under the umbrella of the Universal Basic Education program. The purpose of the study was to assess the UBE program in Nigeria. Six research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted. The target population was 20,000 students and 150 teachers. A random selection gave a sample of 200 students and 15 teachers. Two sets of questionnaires were employed. The simple percentage was adopted for data analysis. The results revealed that the teaching and learning of basic science in the upper basic in Kajuru Local Government Area of Kaduna State has some problems such as lack of qualified and competent teachers, high enrolment of students with lack of adequate facilities. Recommendations were in line with findings.

Sambo et al. (2014) observe that their research was designed to assess the implementation of the basic science program in Junior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa West Zone of Nasarawa state. Specifically, the study intends to find out whether the curriculum content of the Basic Science Program is taught to the students as specified, the availability, adequacy, and utilization of facilities, the quality, and quantity of teachers, the teaching methods employed by teachers and

the performance of students in the Basic Science Program in Junior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (JSSCE) in the state. The assessment of the implementation of the basic science program involves the collection of data and the use of data to assess the effectiveness of the quality of a new science program. A total of eighteen Junior Secondary Schools were sampled and questionnaires were administered to both teachers and students to collect the data. The result of the study revealed these findings. Basic science programs in Nasarawa West Junior Secondary Schools are being implemented to a large extent, facilities available for the implementation of Basic Science Programs are not adequate and there is a significant difference between the mean perception of rural and urban teachers on the extent of the implementation of the basic science program curriculum in Nasarawa West Zone. In conclusion, it has been proved in the course of this study that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in basic science achievement test for junior secondary school students in Nasarawa West Zone. It has also been proved that Nasarawa West Zone has enough qualified teachers that can enhance the implementation of the basic science program in junior secondary schools.

Furthermore, it has been proved that the facilities available for the implementation of basic science programs are inadequate and underutilized. It has also been proved that lecture method, discussion method, group investigation, field trip/excursion, guided discovery, and cooperative method are the methods of teaching commonly adopted by teachers. Recommendations were proffered to enhance the effective implementation of basic science programs in Nasarawa West Zone.

Omorogbe & Ewansiha's (2013) paper attempts to highlight the performance of students in science in Nigeria and some of the factors that affect performance in science. These include Quality Science teaching, Teacher quality, and the five indicators of teacher quality. They include; academic and professional qualification, In-service refresher courses and training, teacher experience, and teacher salary, and quality teaching-learning resources. All these factors affect largely the way science is taught in schools. Regrettably, the teaching and learning of science in Nigerian schools cannot be said to be effective because of the poor performance of students resulting from inappropriate teaching methodologies, lack of adequate knowledge of the subject matter, competencies, skills, inadequate teacher training and lack of in-service training and refresher courses, and lack of basic teaching-learning resources. The way forward to improving science education in Nigeria is also discussed and recommendations and conclusions made.

Alexander et al. (2017) evaluated some factors affecting learning in secondary school. Secondary schools in Otukpo Local Government Area of Benue State were used as a case study. A structured and close-ended questionnaire was developed and systematically administered in order to elicit responses from the respondents. A total of 200 respondents provided responses that were used for analysis. Data analysis was achieved using frequency count, total weighted value, and mean. Respondents agreed that unprofessional teaching practice adversely affect students' learning (mean = 3.53), the use of professional teachers as principals, administrators, form teachers and counselor improve students' academic performance and cover up loop holes (mean = 3.50), a teacher who is sound in his subject area is capable of arousing students interest to learn (mean = 3.71), provision of students primary needs enable them to learn better (mean = 3.59), students from well- to – do parents have advantage of completing the curriculum (mean = 3.50), observing of siesta, when a student is tired, enhances learning (mean = 3.50), practice of personal hygiene helps to eliminate health risk factors and good state of mind for learning (mean = 3.48), proximity and accessibility of a school, encourage learning (mean = 3.54), strike actions disrupt learning activity (mean = 3.48), inconsistent and irregular payment of teachers salary hampers teaching and learning

(mean = 3.61), occasional giving of reward stimulate other students to learn (mean = 3.64), development of positive self-concept by a student helps in brilliant academic performance (mean = 3.53) and students with health challenges find it difficult to learn (mean = 3.52). In line with this finding, it is imperative to state that learning, which is the sole of all academic activity, can be achieved at any level if the above are carefully considered.

Methodology:

The aim of this study is to investigate the challenges facing the implementation of science programs in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria. The questionnaire was adopted for this study by the researchers. We used a descriptive survey design for the study. Simple sampling methods were used to select 140 respondents from the entire population of science teachers in FCT, Abuja. The research questionnaire used was titled “Investigation of the challenges facing the implementation of the science program Questionnaire”. The questionnaire had two parts. Part one solicited for bio-data information of the respondents while part B collected information on the topic of the research. The research questionnaire had eight sub-items questions. The questionnaire adopted liker scale options of Strongly Agree, Agree, Strongly Disagree, and Disagree options for the study. To ensure the validity of the instruments, two evaluation expertise was consulted and they crossed check the questions. The observation made was correct. The reliability of the instrument was determined through the use of test and re-test method. Ten samples of the questions were administered two times to the same people who are also science teachers in a nearby state within two weeks. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used for the reliability test which yielded 0.85 which is a great score for the instruments. The questionnaire was administered directly by the researchers to the respondents in their various institutions. Mean, simple percentage and chi-square were used to analyze and test the hypotheses.

Result Analysis:

1. To find out if the inadequate science teachers is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.715	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

The result collected showed that the Calculated Value obtained was (0.715) and the Table Value (0.195).

2. To find out if the inadequate funding is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.72	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

The result obtained from research question two revealed that the Calculated Value was (0.723), while the Table Value was (0.195).

- To find out if the inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.722	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

Result from research question three disclosed that the Calculated Value was (0.722) and the Table Value (0.195).

- To find out if the inadequate instructional materials is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.725	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

The Calculated Value obtained from table four is (0.725) and the Table Value is (0.195).

- To find out if the poor planning is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.711	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

The result collected showed that the Calculated Value is (0.711) and the Table Value is (0.195).

- To find out if ineffective supervision is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Variable	N	Df	r-cal	t-table	Result
X	140	138	0.723	0.195	Significant
Y	140				

The result obtained from hypothesis six revealed that the Calculated Value obtained is (0.723) while the Table Value is (0.195).

Result Discussion:

- To find out if the inadequate science teachers is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

The reaction of respondents to research question one showed that the Calculated Value obtained was (0.715) and it exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (Hi) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected. This means that inadequate science teachers are a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. Adeniyi (2016) submits that majorities of secondary schools in Nigeria are having the problem of shortage of professional science teachers.

2. To find out if the inadequate funding is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

From the above table the Calculated Value obtained was (0.719) exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (Hi) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected. This implies that inadequate funding is a challenge to the implementation of the science programs in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. This result is in agreement with the observation of Adeniyi (2016) who concluded that inadequate funding is one of the major challenges facing the entire educational system in Nigeria.

3. To find out if the inadequate infrastructural facilities is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Results collected on research question three revealed that the Calculated Value obtained was (0.722) and it exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (Hi) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected. The implication of this result is that inadequate infrastructural facilities are a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. This result is in agreement with the submission of Sambo, Kukwi, Eggari & Mahmuda (2014) they observe that since most of the respondents claim that materials or facilities are not adequate. It can be concluded that facilities available for the implementation of Basic Science Programs in Nasarawa West Senatorial District are not adequate. Omorogbe, & Ewansiha (2013) also support the view above when they submit that the situation in many science classrooms in Nigeria is nothing to write home about. In many schools, there are no laboratories. Some schools merely have empty rooms labeled laboratories. Students rarely have hands-on, minds-on experiences.

4. To find out if the inadequate instructional materials is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

The result collected from the above table disclosed that the Calculated Value obtained was (0.725) and it exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (Hi) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (Ho) was rejected. This means that inadequate instructional materials are a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. Due to the fact that the majority of schools lack the essential resources for imparting the knowledge of science concepts to students, many students learn little science, learning tends to be by rote and many students find science not interesting and boring (Ogunmade, 2006).

5. To find out if the poor planning is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

From the above table the Calculated Value obtained was (0.711) exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (H_i) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (H_o) was rejected. Poor planning is a challenge to the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

6. To find out if the ineffective supervision is a challenge to the implementation of the science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Responses from the sampled respondents revealed that the Calculated Value obtained was (0.723) and it exceeded the Table Value (0.195). Therefore, the Alternate hypothesis (H_i) was accepted, while the null hypothesis (H_o) was rejected. This implies that ineffective supervision is a challenge to the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja. This finding is in support of Adeniyi, (2016) who observes that one of the challenges facing the Nigerian educational system is the ineffectiveness of supervision program.

Conclusion and recommendations:

The objectives of this study were to evaluate the challenges facing the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja, Nigeria. Data/information were collected and analyzed. The result collected from the study led to the conclusion that majorities of the sampled respondents agreed that inadequate science teachers, inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructural facilities, inadequate instructional materials, poor planning and ineffective supervision are the challenges to the implementation of science program in FCT Secondary schools, Abuja.

Based on this findings, the researchers hereby recommended the following:

- i. The government should increase the funding of science education in FCT and in Nigeria in general
- ii. The government should ensure proper planning of education and especially the science program so that it will be easy to implement
- iii. The government should provide more infrastructural facilities like physic, Biology, Chemistry, computer laboratories and more classrooms should be provided for the science students to aid effective teaching and learning of science program
- iv. More professional science teachers should be employed and deploy to secondary schools across FCT, where there is a shortage of science teachers
- v. The government should provide more instructional aids for the teaching of science programs in all the secondary schools in FCT, Nigeria
- vi. The government should ensure that science program are effectively been supervised in FCT by improving the capacity of the inspection and supervision teams in FCT.

References:

- Adeniyi, T. (2016). *Problems facing the teaching and learning of Science subjects in Enugu state. Nigeria*. Unpublished Thesis.
- Alexander, I., Veronica, E. A., Rita, O. N. & Iwebo, E. J. (2017). Evaluation of factors affecting learning in secondary school in Otukpo local government area of Benue state, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Leadership Development*. Volume 9, Number 1. pp. 42-59
- Christine. A. & Hayatu, S. J. (2014). *Universal Basic Education (UBE) in Nigeria problems and prospects in learning basic science in the upper basic : a case study of Kajuru local government area of Kaduna State*. Thesis submitted to the University of JOS Faculty of Education, Department of Science And Technology Education
- Federal Ministry of Education, FME. (2004). *The Basic Science and Technology Curriculum*: Abuja: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN. (2013). *National Policy on Education*, 6th edition: Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Fiifi, M. & Beatrice A., S. (2013). The Teaching of Science: Challenges and Prescription. *Journal of Education and Practice* Vol. 4, No. 22. pp. 116-123
- Legit. (2018). Nigerian curriculum for secondary schools. Retrieved July 24, 2019 from <https://www.legit.ng/1168651-nigerian-curriculum-secondary-schools-2018.html>
- Mulemwa, J. N. (2002). A triangular framework for improving girls participation in STME at the school level in Africa. Kenya. pp. 96 - 101
- Ogunade, T. O Okedeyi, S. A & Bajulaiye A. A. (2006). The Status of Resources in Secondary Science Teaching and Learning in Lagos State Nigeria. *Journal of Science Teachers Association*. Vol. 8, No. 2. pp. 57
- Omorogbe, E. & Ewansiha, J., C. (2013). The Challenge of Effective Science Teaching in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies MCSER Publishing, Rome-Italy*. Vol 2 No 7. pp. 89
- Opara., P. & David U, E.(2014). Factors Affecting Teaching and Learning of Basic Science and Technology in Primary Schools. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research (JEPER)*. Vol. 1, No. 1. pp. 46-58
- Sambo, M. H., Kukwi, I. J., Eggari, S. O. & Mahmuda, A. M. (2014). Assessment of the Implementation of Basic Science Program in Junior Secondary School in Nasarawa West Zone. *Developing Country Studies* Vol. 4, No. 20. pp. 96-99
- Sharf, N., Wajdi, A. (2019). Perception about the Implemented Curriculum at Public Higher Secondary Schools in Sindh. *Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* 1 (II), pp. 28-43

Telima, A. (2019). The Aims and Purposes of Science Education: Social-Scientific Issues in the Science Curriculum in Nigeria. *American Research Journal of Humanities Social Science (ARJHSS)R* *ARJHSS Journal* www.arjhss.com Vol. 3, No. 5. p. |23